

Implementation of a road attribute changes data-exchange platform and a transferability assessment: The case of TN-ITS Cyprus

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Abstract

Following the EU Directive for the EU-wide real-time traffic information services (2015/962) as well as the increasing demand for accurate and high detail maps; map providers and road authorities need to work closely to be able to provide drivers with the most accurate and up-to-date information regarding the road network infrastructure. Drivers access information regarding the road network infrastructure through navigators which contain maps from commercial map providers. However, map providers collect information for the road network after field surveys which take place every few months or years; at the same time, the road network is constantly changing by road authorities following regulation changes. The TN-ITS project aim is to provide the necessary support to create data exchange platforms regarding changes in the road network between road authorities and commercial map providers. This project is expected to close a gap in the information flow between the two parties as well as to increase road safety. This paper describes the implementation of the TN-ITS service in Cyprus, covering the highway and intraurban road network followed by a transferability analysis of the developed platform to assess the possibility of using the same platform to cover a larger area of the road network.

Keywords:

TN-ITS, road network, data exchange

Introduction

Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) are considered as an effective approach that will alleviate many transportation problems such as traffic congestion, high accident rates, air pollution, and potentially will improve safety and reliability on existing road systems through “smarter” use of transport networks [1]. It is notable today that the driving experience is changing with the introduction of new technologies related to ITS such as, build-in vehicle sensors detecting traffic and road conditions helping drivers to reduce their response time in incidents or even adapting the vehicle’s behavior increasing road safety [2]. At the same time, the European Union has introduced the EU Road Safety Policy Framework 2021-2030 – Next steps towards “Vision Zero” which consists of a Strategic Action Plan on Road Safety. To achieve this vision, new technologies related to ITS are an integral part of the policy, while at the same time it is noted that accurate digital maps are crucial to achieving effective ITS [2,3].

Geospatial information in Intelligent Transport Systems

Geographical Information Systems (GIS) are widely used in Transportation (GIS-T) and spatial models were developed for managing transportation systems and sharing data between GIS and Transportation Systems [4]. GIS-T has four main components, encoding; management; analysis and reporting [5]. *Encoding* includes the representation of real-world transportation system and its spatial information as nodes and links; *management* means the generation of a GIS database to store encoded transport data; *analysis* refers to tools and methodologies; and finally, in *reporting* both spatial and non-spatial information are presented for further planning and decision-making [5,6].

Detailed geospatial information representing road networks and any associated data consists of a critical component for route planning and navigation through ITS so that applications can be carried out in real-time [7]. An Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS), provide a functional system-level framework of the technology incorporating and depending on geospatial information for enabling the autonomous or semi-autonomous control of vehicle driving functions [7,8]. This geospatial information facilitates access, retrieval, analysis and representation of a high volume of information. As modern vehicles contain a range of sensors from which they create local geospatial knowledge, they can share this information with map providers and other road users [7]. However, the local knowledge is neither sufficient for route planning nor for local navigation under challenging conditions such as bad weather, bad markings on the road, occlusion of objects since potential sensor inaccuracy and false detection events are possible [9]. For such scenarios, geospatial information from pre-processed databases (such as high definition map datasets) is necessary to compensate the sensor insufficiencies and support ADAS and autonomous driving. Under this perspective, the users of ITS applications rely on accurate and up-to-date geospatial information for the complete knowledge needed for legal and safe navigation [7]. The authoritative source for this information is road authorities, which are responsible for setting the regulations for road use and maintain geospatial information for the road network. However, the information regarding the road network is reaching the road users through navigators which are produced by commercial map providers who collect information regarding the road network infrastructure through surveys.

Problem Statement

ITS application, need maps that are highly up-to-date with consistent and relevant data based on the most accurate information available directly from the source [10]. Maintaining information about static road data that relates to a specific location on the road network, it is a piece of important safety information that needs to be shared reliably with map providers in order the respective attributes for that road segments are updated accurately. Most of the map providers, during the past years, were focused on local large-scale surveys to collect data in a frequency of a few months up to a few years. In the meantime, the road network is constantly changing due to changes in regulations. This creates inconsistency between digital maps and the real world.

Therefore, commercial map providers in order to keep their maps up-to-date need reliable and

harmonized mechanisms from which they can retrieve information from authorities for any changes in the road network for further sharing with the road users [11]. The most reliable source of this information are the authorities responsible for changes in the road network. However, to use these data it is important that the information for any change is using a harmonized mechanism which is consistent in different countries, and enables them to process updates on changes in the road network, such as safety-related attribute data from public road authorities accurately, efficiently and timely.

European Union, in its efforts to leverage their investment in INSPIRE-compliant data and service by making them applicable to a broader range of policies and applications for sharing data between Member States to improve public safety, and reduce the risk of damage to infrastructure, has funded a project to help solving the above problem, by creating the necessary standard for data exchange between road authorities and map providers [10]. Even though the market is already providing such services, there is still a lack of cross-border continuity for high-quality data and intra-EU and internationally data exchange agreements. Recognizing all these needs, an INSPIRE and ITS-related pilot activity introduced by the European Union as a fundamental shift and guidance to effectively resolve these complex problems under the project of “Transport Network ITS Spatial Data Deployment Platform” (TN-ITS) [10].

The objective of this paper is to introduce the implementation of the TN-ITS pilot platform in Cyprus highway and intraurban road network and to assess the transferability of the service to include a larger area of the road network.

Background

The Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2015/962, supplementing the ITS Directive (2010/40/EU) of the European Parliament and Council sets out the requirements to ensure compatibility, interoperability and continuity for the deployment and operational use of ITS for the provision of EU-wide real-time traffic information services [12,13]. The Directive also states the importance of accessibility, exchange and re-use of the road and traffic data set, as well as, the need to facilitate a mechanism to exchange information between road authorities/road operators with digital map providers [14]. Following that need, the project “Transport Network ITS Spatial Data Deployment Platform (TN-ITS)” has a mission to “Facilitate and foster the exchange of ITS-related spatial road data between road authorities as trusted data providers and data users as mapmakers and other parties” [15]. Thus, the purpose of this activity is to create a service in each involved Member State by setting up a pilot or a live service for accessibility, exchanges, re-use and provision of updates of static road data such as speed limits. That eventually will close the gap between road authorities and map providers.

The TN-ITS is considered as an extension of the ROSATTE project (Road Safety Attributes Exchange Infrastructure in Europe) which was funded by the EU (2008 –2010), and coordinated by ERTICO [16]. The TN-ITS consortium includes Sweden and Norway with a fully functional service developed

under the ROSATTE project, aiming to help other countries with their implementations. Then Finland, Flanders, UK, Ireland, and France have already a pilot service running, and they are working to improve it. Also, Netherlands, Hungary, Lithuania, Portugal, Greece, Slovenia, Estonia, Spain, and Cyprus are included in the consortium with the aim to develop a pilot service, publishing updates of at least one road network attribute for a part of their road network. Lastly, HERE and TomTom as representatives of the map providers are working with the EU member states to ensure that the data produced by their TN-ITS services are consistent and usable. Each country has its own road network database with unique characteristics which are usually maintained by the local road authority, however, the information from each country should be published through a standardized form.

Case: The Implementation of TN-ITS in Cyprus

Description

The Republic of Cyprus is taking part in the Program Support Action's (PSA) project TN-ITS GO, which aims to assist Cyprus and eight other European Member States to plan and implement a spatial data exchange platform of changes in static road data [15]. The TN-ITS GO project in Cyprus is managed by the Public Works Department (PWD) of the Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works (MTCW) and it is implemented by the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence (KIOS CoE) of the University of Cyprus under a collaboration agreement [17].

In Cyprus, roads are managed either by the Local Authorities or by the PWD. Motorways, 'A' Roads, Urban Roads and roads constructed after a wide urban planning are managed by the PWD, while the rest of the road network, which mainly includes 'B' roads and local roads, are managed by local authorities. All the information regarding the road network under the authority of the PWD are stored in an INSPIRE based database.

According to the PSA's project, the implementations should be focused on the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T). Thus, the Cypriot implementation of the TN-ITS has as a priority to cover the TEN-T road network in Cyprus, while the second priority will be given to the rest of the road network managed by the PWD. The two types of the road network are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - TEN-T road network in Cyprus (Red) approximate 330 Km and Main Roads (Blue) maintained by the PWD approximate 2,400 Km

Cyprus has followed the “CEN/TS 17268:2018 - Intelligent transport systems - ITS spatial data - Data exchange on changes in road attributes specifications” to develop the TN-ITS service [12]. The specifications are very flexible in terms of the methodology to be followed to develop the functional components which will enable the implementation of the service. In addition, each Member State is free to choose the license under which the data produced from the service will be disseminated. Data from the Cypriot TN-ITS platform will be distributed free and open under the Creative Commons 4.0 license.

The first version of the Cypriot TN-ITS service has been published in May 2019 in the website <http://tnits-cyprus.herokuapp.com/>. The published service is currently in a testing phase, where is connected to a testing server, while the outputs are given to map providers (TomTom and HERE) to evaluate the results and provide feedback to improve the service. The Cypriot implementation is using only open source software to develop all the necessary functional components. The system architecture of the service is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - System architecture of the TN-ITS service implementation in Cyprus

As it was shown, any update on the road attributes (A), is recorded to the “PWD Spatial Database” and through a trigger function (B), the changes are stored in the “TN-ITS Database” that was developed according to the TN-ITS specifications. Once the user request data (1) through the “TN-ITS website”, the request is pushed to the “Data Retrieval” (2) functional component which requests the relevant data from the “TN-ITS Database” (3). The data from the TN-ITS database are then forwarded to the “Data Conversion” functional component (4,5) which is responsible to transform the data in the standardized form described in the CEN/TS 17268:2018. Then, the standardized *.xml file is given to the user through the “TN-ITS website” (6,7). The user can request either the data from the previous day or any changes from a specific day since the launch of the service.

Expansion of the service

The TN-ITS Cyprus service, it is connected to the PWD spatial road network database and thus only information for the road network under their authority can be disseminated through the service. The PWD road network consists of around 10% of the whole road network of Cyprus. However, to have a truly reliable service which will lead always to up-to-date accurate digital maps, a larger proportion of the road network should be supported by the service. The rest of the road network in Cyprus is under the authority of the local authorities. Therefore, it is important that the service developed for the PWD it is expandable and it has the provision to be connected to other databases as local authorities’ databases from which it could retrieve information regarding road changes. In order to assess the possibility and the ability of the developed service to be used by local authorities as well, a transferability analysis has been undertaken which is described in the following chapter.

Transferability assessment

With growing interest in accurate maps, as well as in open data, considering at the same time the decentralized databases of different parts of the road network, an analysis has been carried out to identify if the developed service was easily transferable. A transferable service could assist the local authorities to create similar services to record and share data for road changes. The methodology of the transferability analysis was carried out using a seven-step model (Figure 3) developed by the TIDE

project [18,19].

Figure 3 - TIDE transferability analysis steps [18]

The TIDE transferability analysis refined existing and well-proven findings from literature reviews, case studies, transferability methodologies and integrated them into an easy to apply handbook which was used for the transferability analysis for the current project [18]. The transferability analysis of the project was refined to be applicable for the case of TN-ITS, which led to the identification of key success factors and barriers for a successful implementation of the service in local authorities as well.

Key success factors

The implementation of the TN-ITS service is driven and supported by the funding of the EU as well as from governmental policies and the demand for more accurate maps, as the technology moves towards ITS and automobility. These factors give an advantage to the project for further success. Moreover, justifying the economic outcome from this initiative it is difficult using traditional cost-benefit analysis, unless data from the map providers regarding the relation between the up-to-date maps and the transport efficiency are given for further analysis.

The need for accurate information regarding the road network, especially with the advancement in the area of autonomous and connected vehicles, is another factor that encourages road authorities to share information in order to be able to adapt the technological progression in the area of transportation helping at the same with congestion and mobility problems. Of course, this is influenced by the socioeconomical situation of each country as well as by the size of the city, its transport network and the political commitment for innovation.

Key barriers

Implementing the service for the whole road network is very difficult for Cyprus or for other Members States. This is because there are multiple authorities in most of the countries that are responsible to maintain the different parts of the road network. Therefore, this decentralization makes it difficult for countries to implement one interconnected service to disseminate information about changes at the whole road network. Moreover, and especially for small councils, it is considered as very difficult to cope with technological changes which will enable TN-ITS to work in their road network under their authority. This barrier, can be overcome by positive engagement as well as by providing a step by step technical guidance and funding.

Discussion

The implementation of the TN-ITS service is based on the future forecast demand on accurate, detailed and up-to-date maps, which will be essential for the safe navigation of autonomous vehicles, better route planning and safer trips. It is true that this demand is expected to be larger from the private sector (map providers, automotive companies e.t.c.), however, the local authorities are looking to improve the mobility within their road network, thus this joined effort can be beneficial for both private and public sector. Even though it is difficult to justify and convince road authorities to collect and share data regarding road data changes using financial terms, this can be shown using measures based on the outcome of sharing data for improving transport efficiency. Some proposed measures are discussed below.

Interaction between road authorities and Map providers

A successful TN-ITS service has a provision of a feedback loop. The purpose of the feedback loop is to provide road authorities feedback regarding their published data on changes in their road network. Map providers receive the changes from the road authorities and then they apply these changes to their own digital map after verification and validation. In the case that the new data set is not passing the verification/validation process, the map provider is responsible to send feedback back to the local authorities. This feedback loop can help local authorities to identify potential errors in their local road network database and improve the accuracy of their database.

Policy

In general, a policy can be a strong force to implement new strategies. Some countries like Finland, managed to introduce the necessity of collecting road network changes in their legislation with major success and economic justification. Therefore, such policies can further help the implementation to smaller road authorities as well.

Accurate map demand

The implementation of such services like TN-ITS is usually driven by demand. Therefore, demand in this case, is an additional key success factor. Many stakeholders (automotive companies, map providers, drivers etc.) need more and more accurate and timely data which creates a demand for such

a service.

Robust Data

Accurate digital maps, with high-quality of data from reliable sources, can be a major driver for further development of autonomous driving. Countries with high-quality maps can benefit earlier from the driving automation and consequently having safer and faster travel times supporting economic growth.

Future work

The next steps of the project will be to expand the service and include more attributes that are associated with the road network under the authority of the PWD. Then, the local authorities will be contacted to disseminate the purpose and the benefits of collecting road changes and exchange them using the TN-ITS platform. The above measures will be used for further engagement.

Conclusions

Detailed, accurate and up-to-date maps in the transport industry are vital for the development of ITS, for safer trips, and autonomous driving technologies. However, it is important that the map providers need data from the source in order to increase adequately their map up-to-dateness to support the forthcoming technological advancement in the area of transportation and mobility.

As discussed in the paper, the implementation of services like TN-ITS are mostly driven by demand and policies. The success of this service depends on the ability of the service to be easily transferable and ready to be adopted by local authorities as well. In addition, the consistency, reliability, and the frequency are vital for the map providers to use the data from the TN-ITS service to their detailed digital maps and move closer to truly Intelligent Transport Systems.

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